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**PHYSICS TEACHERS' ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE LITERACY AS A CORRELATE OF
STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PLATEAU STATE,
NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital-driven learning environment, teachers must possess competencies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) literacy to facilitate effective teaching and learning. This study examined the extent to which physics teachers' AI literacy level predicts student academic achievement in senior secondary schools across Plateau State. Adopting a correlational survey research design, the study sampled 36 Physics teachers and 393 physics students drawn from target populations of 311 and 22,985 respectively. Data collection instruments included the Physics Teachers' AI Literacy Assessment Questionnaire (PTAILAQ) and a Physics Students' Academic Achievement Proforma (PSAAP), with the former yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Results revealed that the AI literacy level of teachers was high (HL= 3.56 and mean academic achievement score of 56.23). A statistically insignificant weak positive correlation ($r = 0.146$, $t = 0.862$, $p = 0.395 > 0.05$) was found between teachers' AI literacy and student academic achievement, while multiple linear regression analysis confirming Physics teachers AI literacy and gender as non-significant predictor ($\beta = 0.159$, $t = 0.916$, $p = 0.366 > 0.05$ and 0.86 , $t = 0.496$, $p = 0.623 > 0.05$). Recommendations include, organize regular training and workshops to improve physics teachers' AI literacy and provide access to AI-integrated teaching tools and infrastructure in secondary schools.

Keywords: AI Literacy, Physics Teachers, Academic Achievement, Plateau State, Senior Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) was first defined in 1956 as “the science and engineering of creating intelligent machines” (McCarthy, 2007). In recent years, AI has evolved into a technological domain that leverages natural language processing, neural networks, and machine learning to solve complex problems across various fields (Mondal, 2020). Its applications are rapidly transforming diverse aspects of human life, including medicine, psychology, science, and public policy (Xu et al., 2021). Within education, AI has been increasingly integrated into teaching and learning processes, where it supports teachers in predicting students' learning performance, recommending learning resources, automating assessments, and enhancing

student engagement through intelligent systems such as chatbots and recommendation tools (Liang et al., 2021; Mousavinasab et al., 2021; Su et al., 2022; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2021).

The upsurge of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education has reshaped teaching methods and student participation in learning processes. Specifically, in Physics education, AI supports conceptual understanding through simulations, personalized feedback, and interactive learning environments. The application of AI, however, is only as effective as the educators' ability to use it meaningfully in instructional contexts. Recent developments in AI underscore its potential beyond a mere tool, positioning it as an integral component of the learning ecosystem. This has given rise to the concept of AI literacy, which comprises the knowledge, skills, and ethical awareness required to engage with AI in diverse settings (Long & Magerko, 2020; Southworth et al. 2023). Teachers need this literacy to harness AI for instructional effectiveness.

Despite these advances, young learners often engage with AI applications without adequate knowledge of their underlying principles, raising concerns about misconceptions, ethical issues, and safety risks when AI provides misleading information (Gaube et al., 2021). Consequently, scholars emphasize the necessity of developing AI literacy a set of competencies that enables individuals to understand, evaluate, and use AI critically in everyday life (Ng et al., 2021a, 2021b; Kong et al., 2021, 2022; Long & Magerko, 2020). AI literacy is now recognized as a core 21st-century skill required for learners at all levels, including K–12, to thrive in a digitalized educational landscape (Burgsteiner et al., 2016; Kandlhofer et al., 2016; Steinbauer et al., 2021). In Nigerian secondary schools, Physics is often regarded as a difficult subject, with students perceiving it as abstract, fear inducing, and associated with persistent failure in internal and external examinations (Lawrence & Mankilik, 2020). Such challenges have been linked to passive teaching methods that fail to actively engage learners. Active instructional strategies, such as group discussions, role play, computer-assisted instruction, and the use of AI-based applications, can motivate students and foster better academic achievement (Aliyu, 2022; Ouyang & Jiao, 2021). AI tools such as adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and ChatGPT now provide individualized feedback and problem-solving support in Physics, potentially improving student understanding and academic performance (Halaweh, 2023).

Regardless of the growing presence of AI technologies, there is limited empirical evidence on the preparedness of Nigerian Physics teachers to integrate AI in their classrooms. This study investigates the predictive relationship between Physics teachers' AI literacy level as a correlate of students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Plateau State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Physics continues to pose academic challenges for many Nigerian students, with persistent low achievement levels recorded across schools (Mankilik & Umaru, 2015; Usman & Jilang, 2018; Usman & Mankilik, 2019). Furthermore, the decreased enrolment in Physics has been attributed partly to the difficult and abstract nature of some concepts in the subject as well as the mathematical quantitative contents (Okoronka, 2018). This problem can be partly solved if teachers will utilize artificial intelligence technologies effectively in classrooms to bridge between difficult and abstract concepts; and understanding them. While various factors have been attributed to this persistent poor academic achievement (Okoronka, 2018; Putra et al. 2020; Ibrahim et al. 2024), the influence of AI literacy among Physics teachers remains underexplored. As education shifts towards digital competency, understanding how teachers' AI literacy proficiency affects student outcomes becomes crucial. Thus, the need to carry out this research on Physics teachers' artificial intelligence literacy as a correlate of students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Plateau state, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to determine whether Physics teachers' levels of AI literacy can predict student academic achievement in Plateau State's senior secondary schools. The specific objectives include:

- i. Assessing the AI literacy level among Physics teachers in senior secondary schools in Plateau State.
- ii. Determining the average academic achievement of students' offering Physics in senior secondary schools in Plateau State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What is the current level of AI literacy among senior secondary school Physics teachers in Plateau State?
- ii. What is the mean academic achievement score of students offering Physics in senior secondary schools in Plateau State?

HYPOTHESIS

- i. There is no significant correlation between Physics teachers' level of AI literacy and students' academic achievement in senior secondary school in Plateau State.
- ii. There is no significant interactive correlation of Physics teachers' AI literacy levels, and gender on students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Plateau State.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This study is anchored on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework by Mishra and Koehler (2006). TPACK emphasizes the interconnectedness of technology, pedagogy, and content in achieving instructional effectiveness. In this context, AI literacy represents the technological component necessary for enhancing Physics teaching and learning. Further support is drawn from Bento's (2020) AI Literacy Framework, which defines AI literacy in terms of knowledge (conceptual understanding), skills (application), and attitudes (ethical and critical engagement with AI). The framework underscores the importance of equipping educators with the tools and mindset necessary to thrive in an AI-driven academic environment.

The term "AI literacy" was first coined by Burgsteiner et al. (2016) and Kandlhofer et al. (2016) who describes the competencies to understand the basic knowledge and concepts about AI. On top of this, Long and Magerko (2020) defined it as a set of competencies that enables individuals to critically evaluate, communicate and collaborate effectively with AI; and use AI as a tool online, at home, and in the workplace. Further, Ng et al. (2021a, b) added AI to every student's twenty-first century digital literacy in work settings and everyday life, and proposed it as a fundamental skill for everyone, not just for computer scientists. They widely incorporated the model of Bloom Taxonomy, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK), and AI concepts, practices, and perspectives into the instructional design of AI literacy education.

AI technologies integrate diverse fields such as cognition, data science, machine learning, and decision-making. In education, tools like XR (extended reality), wearable tech, and algorithmic personalization enable differentiated instruction and improved learner outcomes (Zhai et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2020). AI literacy is now regarded as an essential digital competence, fostering critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and responsible AI usage (Kong et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022). Studies have explored AI literacy among various educational levels, including primary, secondary, and higher education, affirming its role in shaping future-ready learners and educators (Lee et al., 2021; Su & Yang, 2023).

Academic achievement, particularly in Physics, refers to the measurable progress of students as reflected in grades, scores, and mastery of concepts (Lawrence & Mankilik, 2020). However, persistent gender imbalances and low retention rates in Physics highlight the need for innovative teaching approaches. Integrating AI into Physics instruction can help reduce these challenges by creating more engaging, personalized, and interactive learning environments (Chun, Ning, Chen, & Wijaya, 2025). Recent empirical evidence shows that AI literacy directly and indirectly influences students' academic achievement through enhanced self-efficacy and creativity (Chun et al., 2025). This suggests that teachers' AI literacy is not only a professional competency but also a critical correlate of students' achievement in science subjects such as Physics. Given the transformative role of AI in education, it becomes imperative to investigate the extent to which Physics teachers' AI literacy influences students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Plateau State, Nigeria. This study, therefore, focuses on examining Physics teachers' AI literacy as a correlate of students' academic achievement, with the goal of informing instructional practices and educational policy in the age of digital transformation.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. The target population consisted of 311 Physics teachers and 22,985 senior secondary three (SSIII) students offering Physics across Plateau State. The SSIII students were considered suitable for the data collection due to their experience in the senior secondary school Physics which made them better than their counterpart juniors. A sample of 393 SSIII students was determined using Taro Yamane's formula and selected by simple random sampling method which followed multiple procedure. Thirty-six schools participated in the research from twelve LGA within the State, each having three senior secondary schools chosen at random. Thirty-six Physics teachers based on the number of randomly selected schools was taken and two instruments were employed: PTAILAQ (Physics Teachers' AI Literacy Assessment Questionnaire) measured AI knowledge, which adapted the Likert scale and modified it to level for this study. The PTAILAQ had ten items with the following response modes Very High Level (VHL) = 5 points, High Level (HL) = 4 points, Moderate Level (ML) = 3 points, Low Level (LL) = 2 points and Very Low Level (VLL) = 1 point. PSAAP (Physics Students' Academic Achievement Proforma) collected existing student performance records. The PTAILAQ instrument was trial tested and yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.83, indicating good internal consistency. Descriptive statistics were used to determine mean scores, while simple linear regression and multiple linear regression analyses were applied to examine relationships and predictive effects. Hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level.

RESULTS

The results of the study are presented in tables and discussions as follows:

Research Question One: What is the current level of AI literacy among senior secondary school Physics teachers in Plateau State?

Table 1: Responses on the Current Level of Artificial Intelligence Literacy Among Secondary School Physics Teachers in Plateau State.

S/N	Statement: n=393	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	I have a basic understanding of AI concepts.	3.69	0.86	HL
2.	I have not received formal training on AI.	3.40	1.22	ML
3.	My self-reported level of AI literacy is generally low.	3.36	1.20	ML
4.	I am unfamiliar with AI-powered tools.	3.06	1.12	ML
5.	I have misconceptions about AI applications	3.00	1.14	ML
6.	My understanding of AI is influenced by their prior experience with technology	4.11	0.92	HL
7.	I recognize the potential of AI to enhance classroom instruction strategy.	3.72	1.30	HL
8.	I have developed my own AI-powered resources for teaching physics.	3.17	1.11	ML
9.	My AI literacy is affected by my access to professional development opportunities.	3.81	1.04	HL
10.	My AI literacy is demanded in this digital age.	4.31	0.79	HL
Grand total average		3.56	1.07	ML

Table 1 examines the current level of AI literacy among the physics teachers. The overall mean score is 3.56 with a standard deviation of 1.07, indicating a high level (ML) of AI literacy level. Several items reflect high levels (HL) of AI literacy, such as my AI literacy is demanded in this digital age (Mean = 4.31, S.D = 0.79). Other items, like I am unfamiliar with AI-powered tools. (Mean = 3.06, S.D = 1.12), I have misconceptions about AI applications (Mean = 3.00, S.D = 1.14, and I have developed my own AI-powered resources for teaching physics. (Mean = 3.34, S.D = 1.48), all fall into the medium level category. The overall result implies that AI literacy level is not an issue among Physics teachers in senior Secondary Schools in Plateau State. Teachers' AI literacy level was found to be high, with a mean score of 3.56.

Research Question Two: What is the mean academic achievement of students offering Physics in senior secondary schools in Plateau State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation for Academic Achievement Scores of Students Offering Physics in Senior Secondary Schools in Plateau State.

Variable	N	Mean	S. D
students' academic achievement	393	56.23	13.45

Table 2 reports the mean academic achievement score of students offering Physics in senior secondary schools in Plateau State. With a sample size of 393 students, the mean academic achievement score is 56.23, with a standard deviation of 13.45. This suggests that on average, students' academic achievement in Physics is moderate, but there is a considerable variation in their achievement levels. The standard deviation indicates a wide dispersion of scores around the mean, highlighting differences in students' academic achievement in Physics in Plateau State.

Testing Hypothesis One: There is no significant correlation between Physics teachers’ level of AI literacy and students’ academic achievement in physics in senior secondary school of Plateau State.

Table 3a: Summary of ANOVA from Linear Regression Analysis of Correlation between Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level and Students’ Academic Achievement in Physics

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	80.156	1	80.156	.743	.395 ^b
	Residual	3666.066	34	107.825		
	Total	3746.222	35			

a. Dependent Variable: students’ academic achievement in physics

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level

The result of analysis in Table 4a provides a summary of ANOVA-based linear regression analysis, which was employed to investigate whether there is a significant correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students’ academic achievement in physics. The results reveal that there is significant correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students’ academic achievement in physics, $F(1, .35) = 0.743, p=0.395 < 0.05$. Since the p-value (0.305) is higher than the predefined significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained

Table 3b: Model Summary Table from Linear Regression Analysis of Correlation between Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level and Students’ Academic Achievement in Physics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.146 ^a	.021	-.007	10.38390

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics AI literacy level

Table 3b shows a model summary that demonstrates how the independent variable accounts for the variance in the dependent variable. The results reveal that 0.7% of the variation in the academic achievement could be attributed to Physics teachers’ AI literacy level. The R-value of 0.146^a reveals that there is a weak positive relationship between Physics teachers AI literacy level and the students’ academic achievement in Plateau State.

Table 3c: Coefficients of Beta from Linear Regression Analysis of Correlation between Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level and Students’ Academic Achievement in Physics

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	44.731	14.079		3.177	.003
	Physics teachers AI literacy level	3.356	3.892	.146	.862	.395

a. Dependent Variable: students’ academic achievement in physics

The result in Table 3c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students’ academic achievement in physics. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.146, $t = 0.862, p=0.395 > 0.05$. This indicates that there is positive strong correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students’ academic achievement in physics in senior secondary schools Plateau State, yet is not significant.

Testing Hypothesis Two: There is no significant interactive correlation of Physics teachers' AI literacy levels, gender and students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Plateau State.

Table 4a: Summary of ANOVA from Multiple-Linear Regression Analysis of Correlation between Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level, Gender, and Students' Academic Achievement in Physics

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	107.267	2	53.634	.486	.619 ^b
	Residual	3638.955	33	110.271		
	Total	3746.222	35			

- a. Dependent Variable: students' academic achievement in physics
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level, Gender

The result of analysis in Table 4a provides a summary of ANOVA-based multiple linear regression analysis, which was employed to investigate whether there is a significant correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students' academic achievement in physics. The results reveal that there is significant correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students' academic achievement in physics, $F(2, 33) = 0.486, p=0.619 > 0.05$. Since the p-value (0.619^b) is higher than the predefined significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained

Table 4b: Summary of Multiple-Linear Regression Analysis of Correlation between Gender, Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level and Students' Academic Achievement in Physics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.169 ^a	.029	-.030	10.50102

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics AI literacy level, Gender

Table 4b shows a model summary that demonstrates how the independent variable accounts for the variance in the dependent variable. The results reveal that 3.0% of the variation in the academic achievement could be attributed to Physics teachers' gender, AI literacy level. The R-value of 0.169^a reveals that there is weak positive correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level, gender and the students' academic achievement in Plateau State.

Table 4c: Coefficients of Beta from Multiple-Linear Regression Analysis of Correlation between Physics Teachers AI Literacy Level, Gender and Students' Academic Achievement in Physics

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	41.168	15.948		2.581	.014
	Physics teachers AI literacy level	3.643	3.978	.159	.916	.366
	Gender	2.026	4.085	.086	.496	.623

- a. Dependent Variable: students' academic achievement in Physics
- b. Predictors: Physics teachers AI literacy levels, Gender

The result in Table 4c indicates the beta coefficient of the multiple linear regression analysis of correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level, gender and students' academic achievement in physics. The result of Physics teachers AI

literacy level showed a beta coefficient of 0.159, $t=0.916$, $p=0.366>0.05$. This indicates that there is no significant positive correlation between Physics teachers AI literacy level and students' academic achievement in physics in senior secondary schools Plateau State. However, Physics teachers AI literacy level by gender based revealed beta coefficient of 0.86, $t=0.496$, $p=0.623>0.05$ which indicates that there is correlation but is not significant. It can be concluded that the interactive correlation Physics teachers' AI literacy level made the unique contribution to explaining students' academic achievement, when the variance explained by all other variables in the model are controlled since it has largest beta coefficient of 0.916.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the relationship between Physics teachers' artificial intelligence (AI) literacy as correlate of students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Plateau State. The findings revealed that teachers demonstrated high level of AI literacy with an overall mean of 3.56. Teachers acknowledged the relevance of AI in contemporary education and recognized its potential to improve instructional delivery. However, some teachers reported limited exposure to AI-powered tools and misconceptions about their applications, reflecting a gap between awareness and practical utilization. This agrees with Liang, Su, and Zheng (2021), who noted that teachers often show positive perceptions of AI in education but lack adequate training for effective integration. Students' academic achievement in Physics was found to be moderate, with a mean score of 56.23. The wide standard deviation indicated notable differences in students' performance, suggesting that while some students are performing well, others continue to struggle. These findings are consistent with Lawrence and Mankilik (2020), who observed that poor performance in Physics is a recurring issue in Nigerian secondary schools, often linked to ineffective teaching strategies and low learner engagement.

The regression analysis showed that Physics teachers' AI literacy had a weak positive but statistically insignificant relationship with students' academic achievement ($r = .146$; $\beta = 0.146$; $p > 0.05$). This suggests that although Physics teachers AI literacy may contribute to student learning, it does not independently explain a significant proportion of variation in students' achievement in Physics. Similarly, when gender was introduced as a moderating variable, the relationship remained weak and insignificant ($r = 0.169$; $\beta = 0.159$, $p > 0.05$). These findings imply that factors beyond Physics teachers AI literacy, such as instructional quality, school resources, and student motivation, may have stronger influences on achievement outcomes. This aligns with the work of Chun, Ning, Chen, and Wijaya (2025), who found that AI literacy contributes to achievement indirectly through mediating factors like creativity and self-efficacy. Overall, the findings highlight that while Physics teachers possess foundational AI knowledge, its practical application in classroom instruction remains limited. The insignificant correlation with student achievement underscores the need for sustained professional development, school support structures, and pedagogical innovations to fully harness AI's potential in improving Physics learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Physics teachers in secondary schools in Plateau State possess a high level of AI literacy, which reflects awareness of its importance but may have limited practical integration into classroom practice. Students' achievement in Physics remains moderate, with significant variations across learners. Although teachers' AI literacy showed a weak positive correlation with students' performance, the relationship was not statistically significant. This implies that teachers AI literacy alone may not directly translate into improved student outcomes without complementary factors such as pedagogical skills, instructional resources, and learner-centered practices. Sustaining teachers' digital competencies, particularly in AI, is essential for fostering innovation and enhancing students' academic achievement in Physics.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following suggestions were reached after carefully analyzing the findings of the study;

- i. Organize regular training and workshops to improve physics teachers' AI literacy.
- ii. Provide access to AI-integrated teaching tools and infrastructure in secondary schools.
- iii. Expand research to include other subjects and regions to build a wide coverage on AI literacy in education.

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